

CHARACTERIZATION OF 3D GEOMETRICAL IMPERFECTIONS OF PULTRUDED GFRP PROFILES: INTRODUCTION OF A NOVEL METHODOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The lack of reliable design guidelines is hindering the use of pultruded glass-fiber reinforced polymer (pGFRP) profiles, despite their many advantages, *e.g.*, non-corrodibility and high strength-to-weight ratio. Initial geometrical imperfections (GIs) are a critical factor in determining the post-buckling behaviour of these profiles, directly affecting their design. The aim of this study is to present an experimental methodology to characterize the GIs of pGFRP profiles to improve the prediction of their structural behaviour. The GIs are measured using a 3D contact coordinate-measuring machine (CMM), allowing for a statistical analysis of their shapes and amplitudes for various cross-sections.

KEYWORDS

GFRP members; 3D contact coordinate-measuring machine; dimensional deviation; geometrical imperfection; local imperfection; global imperfection

INTRODUCTION

The rising costs of repairing and maintaining civil engineering structures have increased the demand for lighter, faster, and more durable constructions, with lower maintenance requirements. Pultruded glass-fibre reinforced polymer (pGFRP) profiles have emerged as a competitive solution due to their high strength-to-weight ratio and non-corrodibility. However, their thin-walled cross-sections and low elastic moduli make them susceptible to high deformability and buckling, with the latter often governing their ultimate limit states design. Therefore, evaluating the shape and amplitude of initial geometrical imperfections (GIs) of pGFRP profiles is crucial to understand their post-buckling behaviour.

To date, there is a limited amount of research available regarding the comprehensive evaluation of GIs of pGFRP members. The first investigation on GI measurements in pGFRP columns was carried out by Yoon (1993), followed by the work of Brooks & Turvey's (1995) on an I-beam cross-section. Zureick & Scott (1997) and Zureick & Steffen (2000) also conducted GI measurements on various pGFRP profiles, while Lane & Mottram (2002) used a surveying theodolite to measure minor-axis out-of-straightness of wide-flange cross-sections. Among the earlier studies on this topic, Mottram *et al.* (2003) characterized cross-section dimensions and measured minor-axis out-of-straightness of pGFRP wide-flange columns in five different sections along their axis.

In more recent years, researchers have conducted studies on the minor axis GIs of pGFRP members. Nguyen (2014) and Nguyen *et al.* (2014) used a displacement transducer to measure out-of-straightness imperfections in C-sections (values between $L/416$ and $L/8705$, L being the member length) and I-sections (values between $L/852$ and $L/2344$). They concluded that the lateral-torsional behaviour of pGFRP beams is very sensitive to the GI and that the limit for out-of-straightness GI set in ASTM D3917 (2015) is very high and inappropriate ($L/240$). In addition, Monteiro (2020) used an arm type 3D coordinate measuring machine to measure out-of-plane displacements in different cross-

sections of pGFRP angle sections. The author found that the out-of-straightness values were low compared to the length (between $L/2080$ and $L/4894$). Recently, in a previous study by the authors (Lazzari, Martins, et al., 2022) the feasibility of measuring global GIs of pGFRP profiles with a 3D coordinate measuring machine (CMM) with accuracy of 0.01 mm was demonstrated; it was also shown that the minor-axis GI is the most relevant global imperfection shape in an I-section profile (maximum amplitude of $L/1765$).

At present, certain standards for pGFRP profiles restrict the maximum values of GIs and dimensional deviations (DDs), see Figure 1. The European EN 13706-2 (2002) and Chinese GB/T 31539 (2015) standards have similar GI and DD limits, while the North American ASTM D3917-15a (2015) standard has less restrictive limits, allowing for greater tolerances in dimensions.

Figure 1: Dimensional deviation tolerances of current standards: EN 13706-2 (2002), ASTM D3917-15a (2015), GB/T 31539 (2015).

Previous experimental studies have not examined the local plate deformation of section walls when determining GIs, which has resulted in inaccuracies and an inadequate methodology for determining GIs. Additionally, many numerical studies struggle to incorporate GI shapes and amplitudes into their models, and some of the assumptions made for GIs do not accurately reflect the structural behaviour due to the lack of sound experimental data and reliable recommendations for designing pGFRP structures with GIs (Anbarasu et al., 2023; Chawla & Singh, 2019; Czapski & Kubiak, 2015; Kubiak et al., 2016; Laudiero et al., 2013a, 2013b; Lazzari, Gonilha, et al., 2022; Nunes, Correia, et al., 2016; Nunes, Silvestre, et al., 2016; Silva et al., 2011; Turvey & Zhang, 2006). To predict the strength of pGFRP members more accurately, obtaining high-precision experimental data from GIs measured from real-scale profiles is critical. Therefore, this study aims to develop a novel methodology for characterizing the shapes and amplitudes of GIs in pGFRP members, enabling more precise computational simulations and analytical calibration of the resistance models for such structural members. In this context, the present study introduces a precise methodology for measuring GIs, encompassing the experimental setup and definition of essential geometrical parameters, including height, width, thickness, corner radius, global GI, and local GI. Additionally, point cloud transformations for shell-type nodes are evaluated to enable improved quantification of plate deformation modes. The proposed methodology is expected to enable the collection of comprehensive data on the GIs of pGFRP profiles, enabling more accurate computational modelling, calibration of design curves, and reliability studies for determining safety factors.

The strength and buckling behaviour of thin-walled members are greatly affected by the initial GIs, which can potentially cause significant reductions of their strength. Therefore, it is crucial to evaluate the shape and maximum amplitude of GIs to develop an accurate procedure for predicting the strength of pGFRP members. Figure 2 illustrates the importance of GIs in predicting the strength of pGFRP members using the direct strength method (DSM). The DSM, developed by Schafer and Peköz (1998) and inspired by an idea of Hancock *et al.* (1994), is based on Winter-type equations (Winter, 1947, 1968). This method offers a straightforward approach for designing thin-walled structural elements, particularly for cold-formed steel structures. A key advantage of the DSM is its ability to effectively

account for buckling and material failure through interactive equations, which are directly influenced by GIs. This study's significance is underscored by the crucial role of GIs in the DSM's effectiveness.

Figure 2: Flowchart displaying the contribution of GIs to adjust the design curves for estimating the ultimate strength of pGFRP profiles using the direct strength method (DSM).

CMM SETUP

The GI measurements were carried out at the Metrological Quality Unit of the Scientific Instrumentation Center of the National Laboratory for Civil Engineering (LNEC) using a 3D contact coordinate measuring machine (CMM), moving bridge type, as shown in Figure 3. The CMM, from DEA Brown & Sharp, model GAMMA 2203, has a measuring volume of 1500 mm (x) × 1000 mm (y) × 1000 mm (z), a resolution of 0.0001 mm and an accuracy of 0.010 mm, with a 95% expanded measurement uncertainty. The measurements performed with this testing equipment are traceable to standards which perform dimensional and geometrical measurement units according to the International System of Units (SI), controlled temperature of 20 °C ± 1 °C and relative humidity not exceeding 65%.

Figure 3: Close-up view of the contact probe used by the 3D coordinate-measuring machine (CMM) to measure the 1152×76×6.35 mm³ pGFRP profile manufacture by Strongwell EXTREN® series 525 (2020).

The CMM consists of three components: a vertical z -direction probe system, a moving bridge for transversal y -direction movement, and a stationary granite table for longitudinal x -direction movement. The Renishaw® PH10M Plus probe system with a TP-20 contact probe is attached to the first component. The stylus has 20 mm of length, 1.4 mm of shaft diameter, 10 mm of extension length, and a 2 mm diameter ruby ball tip.

POINT CLOUD TRANSFORMATION

To geometrically characterize profiles, point discretization is set according to certain requirements. These include a maximum specimen length of 1500 mm, a 50 mm distance between cross-sections, at least three points measured per cross-section wall, and aligned and symmetric points measured on both faces of the same wall for thickness characterization. Additionally, three measurement series are conducted per specimen to assess the repeatability of the measurements and its contribution to the measurement uncertainty. Figure 4 shows point discretization in the profile's cross-section and along the longitudinal x -direction.

Figure 4: Reference point cloud identification: (a) the measured points in the cross-section plane for the 3D measurements and (b) the planes to be measured along the longitudinal direction of the profile.

The CMM generates a four-column matrix with the point code and spatial coordinates along x , y , and z axes (Figure 5-a). Measurements are taken on both faces of each wall, providing nearly complete profile geometry coverage (Figure 4-a). The automated procedure is pre-configured based on profile geometry and has an average measurement speed of 10 points per minute (6 seconds per point) depending on the cross-section complexity.

A point cloud in shell-based form is created to better capture the shape and amplitude of the GIs for computational modelling. The new reference point cloud accounts for points measured on opposing sides of the wall by taking their average location and thickness measurement. In cases where wall segments intersect along the cross-section, interpolation is used to ensure continuity. Likewise, linear interpolation is used to estimate coordinates and thickness values between measured cross-sections. Figure 5-a and Figure 5-b illustrate the transformation process, while Figure 5-c displays a cross-sectional image of an I-section with thickness field colour map to highlight the imperfection values.

Figure 5: Measurements of a pGFRP I-section profile: (a) raw data, (b) shell-type nodes, (c) shell-type surface with thickness field colour map, for an I-section $152 \times 76 \times 6.35 \text{ mm}^3$ pGFRP profile (measurements in mm).

DIMENSIONAL DEVIATION PROCEDURE

The methodology presented provides a comprehensive approach to determine the dimensions of the profiles, including height, width, thickness, and corner radius, as well as the length, in each cross-section plane defined in Figure 4-b. Height is defined as the vertical dimension, width is measured perpendicularly to the minor axis, and thickness is measured at every point along the cross-section. Corner radius is measured using the Pratt method (Pratt, 1987) for profiles with external round corners. The dimensional deviation (DD) is calculated as the relative difference between the nominal dimensions given by the manufacturer and those measured based on reference points shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Dimension reference points and parameters for an I-cross-section.

Figure 7 shows boxplots illustrating the experimental results of DD analysis on an I-section with $I152 \times 76 \times 6.35 \text{ mm}^3$ produced by pultrusion and supplied by Strongwell EXTREN® series 525 (2020). The plots display deviations of the height and thickness from reference dimensions in Figure 6. Each data point reflects a property measured along the profile's longitudinal length. These results are important for understanding cross-section regularity, determining safety factors for reliability analysis, and defining more appropriate tolerances with respect to the ones present in current standards (ASTM, 2015; CEN, 2002; GB/T, 2015). Additional results related to DD of this I-section pGFRP profile can be found in a previous study (Lazzari, Martins, et al., 2022).

Figure 7: Typical dimensional deviation results for an I-section $I152 \times 76 \times 6.35 \text{ mm}^3$: (a) height, (b) thickness of the individual walls (Lazzari, Martins, et al., 2022).

DECOMPOSITION OF GEOMETRICAL IMPERFECTIONS

The GI of thin-walled members is crucial for buckling behaviour and ultimate capacity, but there is a lack of reliable measured data. To address this, a solid approach is needed to classify and quantify GI amplitudes and shapes from pGFRP profiles. The GIs may be derived from a generalized deformation mode composed of different shapes of pure deformation modes (Dinis et al., 2006), each with its shape multiplied by its maximum amplitude. The first generation of thin-walled pGFRP cross-sections has two basic types of deformation modes linked with their buckling modes: (i) global (major/minor-axis flexural and twist shape modes), and (ii) local (simply-simply (SS) and simply-free (SF) wall

elements). I-sections, for example, feature one local deformation mode consisting of both SS and SF modes. Figure 8 shows deformation modes for common pGFRP I-section.

Figure 8: Configuration of deformation modes observed in an I-section column, obtained from an elastic buckling analysis conducted with the *FStr* software (Lazzari & Batista, 2021).

Global GI

Figure 9-a shows the procedure for obtaining the flexural deformation modes vector \mathbf{d} through a linear algebraic technique. The gravity line center of the member is first calculated using the raw data, and then each gravity centre's spatial coordinates are defined as the mean value of the coordinates of each cross-section. From these coordinates, an alignment vector named \mathbf{n} is created, and the flexural deformation mode vector \mathbf{d}_i is obtained through a simple algebraic approach, for the i^{th} cross-section. The minor-axis flexural GI (δ_z) and the major-axis flexural GI (δ_y) are then calculated using Eq. 1 and Eq. 2, respectively. In order to decompose the twist deformation mode, a linear curve fitting method is employed using MATLAB's *polyfit* function (The MathWorks Inc., 2022). The twist mode is decomposed from the angle of inclination (θ_t) of the web for I-sections. Figure 9-b shows a scheme of the twist reference plane and points. For I-section, a one-degree curve fitting is performed using four measured points in the web. Typical results for global deformation modes were reported in a previous study from the authors (Lazzari, Martins, et al., 2022).

Figure 9: Illustrative description of the GI decomposition of the (a) flexural deformation modes and (b) twist deformation mode.

$$\delta_{z_i} = \|\mathbf{d}_{z_i}\| = \left\| \mathbf{g}_{zX_i} - \left(\frac{\mathbf{g}_{zX_i} \cdot \mathbf{n}}{\|\mathbf{n}\|} \right) \frac{\mathbf{n}}{\|\mathbf{n}\|} \right\| \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\delta_{y_i} = \|\mathbf{d}_{y_i}\| = \left\| \mathbf{g}_{yX_i} - \left(\frac{\mathbf{g}_{yX_i} \cdot \mathbf{n}}{\|\mathbf{n}\|} \right) \frac{\mathbf{n}}{\|\mathbf{n}\|} \right\| \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Local GI

The imperfect member can be decomposed into pure modes as previously illustrated in Figure 8. The local deformation mode can then be isolated by subtracting the flexural and twist modes. To

decompose the local deformation mode, each wall is treated as an independent element and considering the boundary constraint of each wall segment's intermediate nodes. The wall segments in the member can be categorized into two types: (i) flange elements and (ii) web elements. Flange elements have only one intersection node and are referred to as simply-free (SF), while web elements have two intersection nodes and are referred to as simply-simply (SS). At the intersection points where the flange and web elements meet, known as the web-flange junctions, pinned constraints are located on the longitudinal nodes. Specifically, SS wall segments have two intersection nodes, and therefore two longitudinal nodes where pinned constraints are placed, while SF wall segments have only one intersection node and one corresponding longitudinal node constrained. Figure 10 shows the step-by-step procedure for decomposing local GIs, which includes (i) shell type transformation, (ii) flexural and (iii) twist mode removal, and (iv) assessment of local imperfection at the orthogonal system xyz .

Figure 10: Schematic illustration of the step-by-step procedure for the evaluation of local deformation mode.

The initial stage, explained in POINT CLOUD TRANSFORMATION section, involves converting raw data into shell-type reference nodes (\mathbf{p}_1). The points are arranged in a matrix grouped by the i^{th} cross-section, j^{th} wall segment, and k^{th} point. The second step is to assess the flexural modes, which subtracts the flexural vector \mathbf{d} from the shell-type points in the first step \mathbf{p}_1 , given a new reference node called \mathbf{p}_2 illustrated in Eq. 3.

$$\mathbf{p}_{2ijk} = \mathbf{p}_{1ijk} - \mathbf{d}_i \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

The third step (Eq. 4) involves removing the twist mode, using a reference point at the intersection node for rotating the wall element with a negative value of the degree of twist. The reference point is the junction point of the wall segment (indicated by $k = I$) for the i^{th} cross-section and j^{th} wall,

$$\mathbf{p}_{3ijk} = \mathbf{p}_{2ijI} + (\mathbf{p}_{2ijk} - \mathbf{p}_{2ijI}) \mathbf{R}_x|_{\alpha=-\theta_{ti}} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where $\mathbf{R}_x|_{\alpha=-\theta_{ti}}$ represents the rotational matrix around the longitudinal axis x by a twist angle of $-\theta_t$ at the i^{th} cross-section.

The local deformation mode is obtained after the second and third phases, but it is not properly aligned and centered due to the misalignment of the CMM during measurements. To correct this, the Euler-Rodrigues formula (Dai, 2015) is used to rotate the vector (\mathbf{s}) with a given axis (\mathbf{u}) and angle of rotation (ϕ). The matrix form of the equation is given by Eq. 5,

$$\mathbf{p}_{4ijk} = \mathbf{u}_j(\mathbf{u}_j \cdot \mathbf{s}_{ijk}) + \cos \phi_j (\mathbf{u}_j \times \mathbf{s}_{ijk}) \times \mathbf{u}_j + \sin \phi_j (\mathbf{u}_j \times \mathbf{s}_{ijk}) \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where \mathbf{s} is defined as the vector from the intersection point ($k = I$) at the first cross-section ($i = 1$) given from step 2, to each measured point in step 3; \mathbf{u} is given as the unitary vector perpendicular to the plane formed by the canonical base vector $\mathbf{e}_1 = [1 \ 0 \ 0]$; \mathbf{n} is the vector that consists of the difference between the coordinates of the first ($i = 1$) and last point ($i = N_s$), for the intersection point ($k = I$), given in step 2; ϕ is the negative angle between the vectors \mathbf{n} and the natural base \mathbf{e}_1 .

The results of the local deformation mode are treated as isolated plate elements with the classified boundary constraints previously defined (SS and SF wall segments). Figure 11 shows a typical result of the local deformation mode on an I-section with 3D shape and thickness field colour map, and Figure 12 shows the local deformation along the 2D axis in longitudinal and transversal directions.

Figure 11: Local deformation mode step-by-step (rows) in a pGFRP I-section $I152 \times 76 \times 6.35 \text{ mm}^3$ for each wall segment (columns) of the cross-section.

Figure 12: 2D projection of local GI: (a) SF wall element along longitudinal direction, (b) SF wall element along transversal direction, (c) SS wall element along longitudinal direction, and (d) SS wall element along transversal direction.

FINAL REMARKS

This study has brought attention to the limitations of previous experimental and numerical investigations in accurately determining the structural behavior of pGFRP structures with GIs. The challenges of incorporating GI shapes and amplitudes into computational models and the need for trustworthy recommendations for designing such structures have been identified. This highlights the importance of further research in this area to improve the accuracy and reliability of GIs in the design and analysis of composite structures.

To address these limitations, this study presented a novel methodology for characterizing the shapes and amplitudes of GIs in pGFRP members, which facilitates more precise computational simulations and analytical calibration of the ultimate capacities of these structural members. The methodology presented in this paper is expected to provide high-precision experimental data on GIs measured from real-scale GFRP profiles produced through the pultrusion method. With more accurate data, computational models can be developed to predict the strength of pGFRP members more accurately, and comprehensive recommendations can be made for designing pGFRP structures with GIs. These results may also be leveraged for reliability studies to provide a more precise range of geometric measurement tolerances and safety factors for designing pGFRP structural members.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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